

O PSYCHOLOGY IS IMPORTANT FOR OUR LIFE

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www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10521575

Key words: father of psychology, feelings, brain function, phenomena ,natural sciences, social sciences, focusing, children' psychology,

You can learn and think clearly about psychology, Why we need this subject ? What is important in psychology ? Children' psychology, How we learn it ? from this article. Also, you can write new article from it...

Psychology is one the well-known subject ,which is important to people's brain and life .Not only people, but also animals' life ,their thinking and brain working situations. Walk into any bookshop today and an array of books from Daniel Kahneman's Thinking Fast and Slow to Martin Seligman's Authentic Happiness will confront you. Take a look at the books that came out last year and see the influence the psychological and behavioural sciences have on our everyday lives.

Maria Konnikova's discourse on the Art of the Con, Adam Grant's glimpse into originality, Angela Duckworth's treatise on grit and Frans de Waal musings on whether we are smart enough to know how smart animals are all psychological tracks that graced the bookshelves.

The Queen of the American Talk Show, Oprah Winfrey, not only raises the profile of serious and pop psychology authors but has also raised the role of the profession itself from Dr Phil McGraw to her new protege Toronto psychotherapist, Dr Anne Dranitsaris. All of them , psychology can give informations and advices .Psychology is the scientific study of the mind and behavior. Psychologists are actively involved in studying and understanding mental processes, brain functions, and behavior.Psychology is such a vast field the benefits are wide ranging, it could include researching mental health to help enhance wellbeing, better understanding the relationships we form, self-improvement, or battling addiction. There can also be benefits to our communication with, and understanding of, other people.Psychology includes the study of conscious and unconscious phenomena, including feelings and thoughts. It is an academic discipline of immense scope, crossing the boundaries between the natural and social sciences.Wilhelm Wundt is the man most commonly identified as the father of psychology. 1 Why Wundt? Other people such as Hermann von Helmholtz, Gustav Fechner, and Ernst Weber were involved in early scientific psychology research, so why are they not credited as the father of psychology?

Sigmund Freud. When you think about psychology, the first name that comes to your mind is Sigmund Freud. ...

William James. Through his work, he has established psychology as a branch of science. ...

Susan Blackmore. She is a great psychologist. ...

Martin Seligman. ...

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Communication is essential in any field, but even more so in psychology. It is the principal and is the hallmark of what a psychologist does. Psychology is about understanding human behavior and what can predispose humans to act in a specific manner.

Of course, if we have any problem, our parents try to solve the problem. Perhaps, your friend give advices to you. After that, you feel good and continue your life. This is psychology. Because your brain is working with you and you feel and you can do it. Psychology is very interesting subject. It can change you. During learning psychology, your life is improving. We can learn this subject from everything: people's life, feelings, their mood, animals' actions, also you can read interesting books about it. In every best libraries, there are great deal of psychological books. You can read psychologists' books, such as Ivan Pavlov, William Jeymes, Albert Bandura, Kurt Levin, Viktor Frankl, Ana Freyd, Jak Lakan and others... These people try to learn about type of the psychology. These are the best concentrations in Psychology:

Research/Experimental Psychology.

Forensic Psychology.

Health Psychology.

Industrial/Organizational Psychology.

Neuropsychology.

Social/Personality Psychology.

Sports Psychology.

Quantitative and Measurement Psychology. Psychology is such a vast field the benefits are wide ranging, it could include researching mental health to help enhance wellbeing, better understanding the relationships we form, self-improvement, or battling addiction. There can also be benefits to our communication with, and understanding of, other people. Child psychology is one of the many branches of psychology. This particular branch focuses on the mind and behavior of children from prenatal development through adolescence.¹ Child psychology deals not only with how children grow physically, but also seeks to better understand their mental, emotional, and social development as well. Children is like a paper. Their talents and thinking are very unusual. Their psychology is interesting type of the this subject.

Though we can cite instances of scientists and philosophers "doing" psychology as far back as ancient times, and psychological questioning picked up during the Enlightenment period in Europe, psychology did not emerge as a formal field of study and experimentation until around the 1830s. Nevertheless, psychology is a uniquely modern field, always growing, shifting, and adding to its scope. Most people have taken a psychology class, whether in college or high school, but many are not aware of how present psychology is in many aspects of our lives.

The five basic areas of child psychology are: development, milestones, behaviour, emotions, socialisation.

Child psychology puts great emphasis on the behaviour and mind of children, from prenatal development through the adolescent years. It deals with how children grow physically and through their social, mental, and emotional development.

Psychology aims to change, influence, or control behavior to make positive, constructive, meaningful, and lasting changes in people's lives and to influence their behavior for the better. This is the final and most important goal of psychology.

To conclude, our body, live, time need this subject. Psychology is necessary for everyone.

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